

Damage analysis of thermal-shock failure in isostatically pressed carbon-bonded refractories for continuous casting of steel

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Abstract

In refractory engineering, evaluating thermal shock resistance is essential. Yet, for some applications standardized tests may not fully characterize the processes of damage development and failure. To analyze failure mechanisms in refractories enabling continuous casting of steel a novel thermal shock test was developed. The test simulates ascending heating of severity typical for the service conditions. Samples' geometry is representative of that of service pieces. Several isostatically pressed carbon-oxide materials of different brittleness at failure were tested for in situ monitoring. An infrared temperature measurement, contact extensometers, as well as non-contact methods of digital image correlation and Laser Doppler Vibrometry were used. Regarding the novelty of Laser Doppler Vibrometry for damage assessment in refractories, this method was validated by a series of stress-strain tests where the damage was also quantified by stress-strain data employing cyclic stress-strain protocols. During the thermal shock tests materials of different brittleness demonstrated a wide range of possible failure modes, including instantaneous cracking throughout the sample thickness, gradual crack growth, and damage formation without pronounced crack localization. The modes of failure corresponded with the standardized thermal shock index ranking. In-situ non-destructive tests were especially beneficial for the analysis of non-brittle failure.

Key words: Thermal shock testing; Carbon-bonded materials; Failure modes; Damage Assessment; Non-destructive Testing

1 Introduction

Carbon-oxide refractories are widely used in high-temperature industrial applications, where thermal shock resistance is critical to their performance. The severity of thermal shock and the extent of damage formation are influenced by several factors including the geometry, size of the shocked body, boundary conditions, and material properties ^[1]. Therefore, to assess the thermal shock resistance of refractories, it is essential to replicate service conditions as closely as possible, which is often not the case when using conventional thermal shock tests.

Thermal shock damage assessment can take place after tests or *in situ*, using, for example, Non-destructive Testing methods (NDT) such as Acoustic Emission and Ultrasonic Testing, which provide better insights into the crack formation process. However, many established NDT techniques require waveguides and sensors to be attached to the sample during thermal shock tests ^[2]. In this respect, non-contact techniques such as Digital Image Correlation (DIC) and Laser Doppler Vibrometry (LDV) are advantageous.

This study discusses the newly developed thermal shock set-up by closely simulating field conditions experienced by carbon-bonded flow control refractories and explores the use of *in situ* damage assessment. The contact method, LVDT, and non-contact methods, including DIC and LDV were used to track the development of micro and macro cracks during the test without the need for waveguides. The validity of the signals detected by LDV was verified through acoustic emission signals recorded during a cyclic three-point bending test conducted at room temperature.

2 Experimental Procedures

2.1 Starting Materials

Three isostatically pressed model mixes of refractories for continuous casting of steel were tested (Tab.1). MA is the most brittle material, and MC the least brittle. The thermal shock parameter was calculated as $R'' = D/E \cdot \alpha$, where D is the thermal diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$), E is the Young's modulus (GPa), and α is the coefficient of thermal expansion (K^{-1}). The properties at 900 °C were used. The brittleness ratio was assessed as the ratio of the specific fracture energy (G_f) to the nominal tensile strength (σ_{NT}) measured during the wedge-splitting test.

Table 1: Overview of the general properties of the studied materials

General properties of the materials	MA	MB	MC
Carbon (%)	20	20	25
Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	-	80	75
ZrO ₂ (%)	80	-	-
*R''(900°C)	0.27	0.45	1
*G _f /σ _{NT} (μm) (RT)	0.55	0.75	1

* Properties are shown as normalized to those of MC.

2.2 Testing Methods

Ring-shaped samples with a height of 22 mm were cut from isostatically pressed test pots. Two vertical flat surfaces were introduced opposite to each other to facilitate the localization of crack formation and to enable accurate displacement measurement. The inner and outer diameters of the specimens were 100 mm and 120 mm, respectively.

During the test, the inner wall of the specimens was rapidly heated using induction. An infrared camera was used to assess the temperature distribution during the test, focusing on two key points: T_{inner} and T_{outer}, representing the temperatures on the inner and the outer surface of the specimen.

LVDT (Linear Variable Differential Transformer) measured the horizontal displacement between the extensometer pins on the vertical flat surface. The strain indicated in Fig.6 is calculated from the displacement measured by the LVDT. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) captured the full-field displacement (Fig.1). LDV monitored vibrations induced by damage formation, using the Doppler effect to measure velocity by comparing the phase shift between the reference and reflected beams [3][4]. The frequency shift correlates with the specimen's velocity, indicating damage progression, based on the principle illustrated in the schematics in Fig.2.

Figure 1: Experimental setup of the thermal shock test

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of the Laser Doppler Vibrometry (LDV) principle

Figure 3: Experimental setup of cyclic bending test

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Validation of LDV Measurements

As LDV is a relatively new technique for testing refractories, it was validated using stress-strain tests at room temperature. It was applied during cyclic three-point bending, in parallel with acoustic emission (AE) measurements. The AE measurements followed the approach described in the study [5]. During this test, the LDV laser targeted the middle-bottom part of the rectangular specimen (Fig.3).

Notched and non-notched specimens were tested using the same loading and unloading program. For all materials, notched specimens exhibited brittle failure, while non-notched MB and MC specimens showed post-failure strain softening (Fig4.d). AE signals were registered even during initial loading peaks of lower intensity, the amount of signals increased with the increase of the peak intensity. Also, occasional LDV peaks were registered during loading and were less frequent than AE signals. At failure, the velocity peaks were much higher than the LDV signals registered during loading. During unloading, NDT recordings indicate progressive damage growth. The amount of AE events and LDV peaks increased with the ductility of the materials (Tab.2 and 3).

The notched samples demonstrated less brittle damage progress. In these samples, differences in LDV velocity peaks during loading, peak force, and unloading, were less significant, This may indicate a more gradual damage process of failure, consisting of

several major damage formation occurrences. Velocities at the highest LDV peaks registered at failure in the samples without notch were two times higher than LDV signals recorded in the notched samples. Although LDV is seen as a less sensitive technique than AE, LDV measurements can capture major events at damage formation. It is seen as capable of providing semi-quantitative info on the process of failure.

Figure 4: AE events and LDV velocity peaks during the cyclic three-point bending test for samples MA (a), MB (b), MB with a notch (d), and MC (c)

Table 2: AE data for notched samples during the bending test. CV refers to the Coefficient of Variation

Materials	Total AE events (CV %)	
	Loading	Unloading
MA	928 (22%)	145 (27%)
MB	1750 (4%)	160 (42%)
MC	1826 (12%)	499 (27%)

Table 3: LDV data for the bending test. CV refers to the Coefficient of Variation

Materials	Velocity peak counts (CV %)		Number of peaks at failure	Peak velocity at failure (m/s)
	Before failure	After failure		
MA	3 (16%)	0 (0%)	1	0.0085 ± 0.0001
MB	2 (47%)	1 (47%)	1	0.0095 ± 0.0017
MC	2 (61%)	4 (85%)	1	0.0099 ± 0.0012
MB Notched	2	5	1	0.0050

3.2 Thermal Shock Results

During the test, both rapid heating and gradual cooling were monitored. The inner surface of the specimen was heated up to 1500 °C, and the maximum thermal gradient between the inner and outer surfaces was 450 °C (Fig.5). Cooling was not controlled as the induction was solely switched off.

Figure 5: Example of inner, outer, and the temperature difference ΔT during the thermal shock test

The displacement and LDV measurements showed rather different failure processes in the three tested materials. For MA, the strain increase was followed by a sudden jump. At this moment the specimen split into two parts by a vertical crack (Fig.7). The LDV velocity signal for MA showed no significant peaks before the dominant one at failure (Fig.6.a). From DIC, the residual full-field displacement after sample cooling (Fig.8) further displayed a sharp division into two sections, tracing the crack trajectory. This behavior of MA is consistent with its low R'' and ratio G/σ_{NT} , indicating high brittleness of the material (Tab.1).

MB exhibited a gradual strain increase with a noticeable but less abrupt jump compared to MA, resulting in vertical cracks (Fig.7). After crack initiation, the strain continued to increase and eventually plateaued despite the rising temperature (Fig.6.b). No through-cracking was observed. During heating, LDV signal activity was higher than in MA and lower than MC, and the predominant velocity peak corresponding to the crack formation was detected. During cooling, LDV detected significant velocity peaks at around 700°C, likely due to thermal stress relaxation and the formation of micro cracks or friction between closing cracks sides. The strain at which crack formation occurred was 0.29 % and 0.3% for MA and MB, respectively.

For MC, no abrupt increase in strain was observed. However, similar to MB, LDV velocity peaks started before the onset of damage which occurred at 0.4% of strain (Fig.6.c) and became more frequent as the outer temperature increased implying gradual damage formation. Upon cooling, MC had no visible cracks (Fig.7) but showed a residual strain of 0.09% (Fig.8) confirming the damage formation

process indicated by the LDV.

Thermal shock LDV data was rather different for the three materials. The velocity peak at damage onset registered for MA MB and MC were 0.00865 m/s, 0.00332 m/s, and 0.00254 m/s respectively. As was seen in the bending test, the amount of LDV peaks increased with reduced brittleness.

Figure 6: Outer temperature, strain, and LDV evolution for MA (a), MB (b), and MC (c) materials during the thermal shock test

Figure 7: MA, MB, and MC after the thermal shock test

Figure 8: Residual full-field planar displacement of MA, MB, and MC at the end of the test (after cooling)

4 Conclusions

The novel thermal shock test aims at simulating conditions relevant to the failure of carbon-bonded refractories used for the continuous casting of steel. During the test model materials of different brittleness demonstrated a wide range of possible failure modes, including instantaneous brittle cracking throughout the sample thickness, crack formation with the crack growth arrest, and thermal shock without pronounced crack localization. Thermal shock test results coincide with the ranking obtained from the thermal shock index and brittleness ratio.

The measurement technique LDV was applied to monitor damage formation in refractories in a non-contact regime. Although less sensitive than AE, LDV was found capable of registering major events of damage formation and to provide semi-quantitative information on the intensity of failure.

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References

- [1] T. Lu, N. Fleck, The thermal shock resistance of solids, *Acta Materialia* 46 (13) (1998) 4755–4768.
- [2] K.Makarian, S. Santhanam, Z. N. Wing, Thermal shock resistance of refractory composites with zirconia and silicon-carbide inclusions and alumina binder, *Ceramics International* 44 (11) (2018)12055–12064. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceramint.2018.03.217>.
- [3] S. Vanlanduit, J. J. Dirckx, Editorial special issue on "laser doppler vibrometry", *Optics and Lasers in Engineering* 99 (2017) 1–2. doi:[10.1016/j.optlaseng.2017.09.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlaseng.2017.09.007).
- [4] S. Rothberg, M. Allen, P. Castellini, D. Di Maio, J. Dirckx, D. Ewins, B. Halkon, P. Muyshondt, N. Paone, T. Ryan, H. Steger, E. Tomasini, S. Vanlanduit, J. Vignola, An international review of laser doppler vibrometry: Making light work of vibration measurement, *Optics and Lasers in Engineering* 99 (2017) 11–22, laser Doppler vibrometry. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optlaseng.2016.10.023>.
- [5] K.Andreev, N. Shetty, E. Verstryngge, Acoustic emission based damage limits and their correlation with fatigue resistance of refractory masonry, *Construction and Building Materials* 165 (2018) 639–646.